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Self-Esteem As Correlate Of Academic Engagement Among Public Secondary School Students In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined self-esteem as correlate of academic engagement among public secondary school students in Anambra State. Five research questions guided the study and five null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 21,272 senior secondary school two (SSII) students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population comprised of 9550 male students and 11,722 female students. The sample of the study was 334 (male and female) secondary school students from the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A multistage sampling technique was employed to determine the sample of the study. The instruments for data collection were three instruments: Ronserberg (1965) Self-esteem Scale (RSES) and (2011) Students Academic Engagement in the Schools Questionnaire (SESQ). Since the instruments were standardized and extensively used, they were not subjected to re-validation and reliability. Pearson Product Moment Correlational analysis and multiple regression were used to analyze the data for the study. The findings of the study revealed that, there was a high positive relationship between self-esteem and students' academic engagement. Also, there was a significant high positive relationship between self-esteem and academic engagement among male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The researcher concludes based on the findings of the study that self-esteem has significant relationship with students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on these findings, it was recommended among others that administrators of public secondary schools should collaborate with curriculum planners to integrate subjects and academic activities that promote self-esteem among students. It was also recommended that principals of public secondary schools should organise programmes that help boost students' self-esteem, such as mentorship schemes, peer-support initiatives and confidence-building exercises.

Keywords: academic engagement, self-esteem, students

INTRODUCTION

The term academic engagement is commonly used to describe the level of involvement and investment that students have in their school experience (Abid& Akhtar, 2020). Ohamobi and Ezeaku (2015) defined students' academic engagement as a popular phrase used to characterize a student's relationship with the school. It is one of the concepts and variables used to assess the interactions between students and schools. Other terms relating to student academic engagement include school connection, school bonding, school atmosphere, school involvement and school engagement. Academic engagement encompasses both the psychological and behavioural aspects of students' connection to the school. Psychologically, academic engagement refers to students' sense of identification and appreciation for the outcomes of their schooling (Wang et al., 2015). It involves a feeling of belonging within the school community and an acceptance of the values and principles

upheld by the educational institution. Students who are psychologically engaged in school tend to have a positive attitude towards their academic pursuits and may view their education as meaningful and relevant to their lives. Behaviourally, academic engagement relates to students' active participation in a range of academic and non-academic activities within the school. This includes involvement in classroom discussions, completion of assignments and participation in extracurricular activities such as clubs, sports, or community service. Students who are behaviorally engaged in academics demonstrate a proactive approach to their education, seeking opportunities to contribute, learn and grow beyond the confines of the traditional classroom. In the same vein, Ma and Wang (2022) identified the dimensions of academic engagement that is affective, behavioral, cognitive, social and concluded that it is a meta-construct. Affective engagement means to learn from experience, behavioral engagement means active participation in activities, cognitive engagement means learning strategies to attain the objective and social engagement means student interpersonal skills

The concept of academic engagement recognizes that students' success and well-being go beyond academic achievement alone. It acknowledges the importance of creating an inclusive and supportive school environment that fosters students' sense of belonging and encourages their active participation in various aspects of school life (McFarland et al., 2018). McFarland et al., further noted that when students feel connected to their school, both psychologically and behaviorally they are more likely to experience positive educational outcomes, develop a sense of personal fulfillment and establish meaningful relationships with peers and teachers. Abid et al., (2022) averred that educators and researchers often use the notion of engagement to better understand and enhance students' overall school experience. Schools may build an engagement culture that supports students' holistic development and maximizes their potential for academic success and personal growth by fostering a sense of belonging, valuing students' viewpoints and providing opportunities for their involvement. Academic engagement in the context of this study is defined as students' involvement and commitment to learning activities especially as it pertains to teaching and learning activities in the classroom. Sadly, the level of academic engagement in some secondary schools in Anambra State appears to be poor. According to Anierobi et al., (2022 p. 15), "public secondary schools have found it very difficult to optimally engage students in academic and non-academic activities" The researcher is worried that if this situation is left unchecked, it will have a negative effect of the quality of human capital in the state. It is therefore necessary to determine the factors that could contribute to poor student engagement. This situation can be attributed to factor like self-esteem.

Self-esteem has garnered increasing attention as a significant factor influencing students' academic engagement. Self-esteem refers to a person's sense of worth and personal importance. Onwubiko (2020) defined self-esteem as one's level of appreciation and like for oneself. It is a value that conveys information about oneself. Self-esteem is a stable and permanent personality attribute that includes appraisals of one's appearance, beliefs, feelings, and behaviours. Omeodu (2021) defined self-esteem as individuals' perception or personal assessment of their self-worth, encompassing feelings of self-respect, self-confidence, and the degree to which one holds positive or negative opinions about oneself. Murphy et al., (as cited in Omeodu, 2021) saw self-esteem as a tool for gauging self-worth, involving both cognitive evaluations of overall self-worth and emotional experiences linked to these broad assessments. Self-esteem is essentially a measure of how much individuals value themselves, constituting the evaluative aspect of self-knowledge. Balakrishnan and Fernandez (2018) defined self-esteem as a complete appraisal of one's value. It reflects an overall perception of one's worthiness or lack thereof (Amos et al., 2016). As an attitude toward the self, self-esteem is closely tied to personal beliefs regarding one's skills, abilities, social connections, and future prospects. While self-esteem and self-concept are often used interchangeably, they are distinct concepts.

Self-concept refers to the overall idea of who a person thinks they are. It includes the beliefs, traits, competencies, and values that an individual uses to describe himself (Meerah & Mazlan, 2017). Self-concept is developed through interactions with others and comparisons to others (Jhoselle, 2020). Self-esteem, on the other hand, is an emotional evaluation of one's self-worth or how much a person values himself. Self-esteem pertains to the emotional responses individuals experience when contemplating and evaluating different aspects of themselves (Lim & Lee, 2017). In essence, self-esteem represents an individual's cognitive and emotional perception of their own value. Abdel-

Khalek (2016) outlined three primary ways in which the term "self-esteem" is employed: (a) global or trait self-esteem, which reflects individuals' typical feelings towards themselves, such as self-affection; (b) self-evaluation, referring to how individuals assess their various abilities and attributes; and (c) feelings of self-esteem, which denote momentary emotional states, such as a person experiencing heightened self-esteem following a significant achievement or a decline in self-esteem following a challenging event like a divorce. Cherry (2019) explained that in psychology, the term self-esteem is used to describe a person's overall sense of self-worth or personal value. In other words, how much you appreciate and like yourself. Self-esteem is often seen as a personality trait, which means that it tends to be stable and enduring. Self-esteem can involve a variety of beliefs about oneself, such as the appraisal of your own appearance, beliefs, emotions, and behaviours.

Self-esteem can be high and low. High self-esteem refers to a positive and favorable evaluation of oneself. Individuals with high self-esteem typically possess a strong sense of self-worth, confidence in their abilities, and a positive outlook on life (Lim & Lee, 2017). They tend to believe in their own capabilities and value themselves highly, which often leads to a greater resilience in the face of challenges, healthier interpersonal relationships, and a greater willingness to pursue and achieve goals. High self-esteem is linked to confidence, happiness, and self-respect, whereas low self-esteem can lead to anxiety, lack of confidence, and self-criticism. On the other hand, low self-esteem refers to a negative and unfavorable evaluation of oneself. Individuals with low self-esteem often harbor feelings of inadequacy, worthlessness, and self-doubt. They may have a pessimistic view of their abilities and may struggle with self-acceptance and self-confidence (Kariuki et al., 2019). Low self-esteem can lead to difficulties in various aspects of life, including relationships, academic or professional performance, and overall well-being. Self-esteem is a key predictor of personal and social well-being. Positive experiences, such as achievement and excellent opinions, can lead to better self-esteem.

Self-esteem, whether high or low, is dependent on how students appraise their own value. The level of self-esteem one holds can have a significant impact on one's academic engagement and across various human endeavour. Extreme high self-esteem can manifest in individuals viewing themselves as superior to others, potentially leading to behaviours like arrogance, selfishness, and difficulty in interpersonal interactions (Kariuki et al., 2019). Such behavioural patterns may have implications for academic engagement. In this study, self-esteem is defined as to students overall sense of self-worth or personal value. It reflects how much a student appreciates and accepts themselves, encompassing beliefs about oneself as well as emotional states, such as pride, shame, and confidence.

Despite teachers' efforts to foster active learning and maximize students' success. Poor students' engagement in secondary schools in Anambra state is evident in behaviours such as poor reading habits, excessive attachment to cell phones, frequent tardiness, and social withdrawal among students (Okeoma et al., 2024). Furthermore, the researcher observed that poor student academic engagement in some secondary schools in Anambra State is evident in the failure of some public secondary schools to effectively organize activities like prize-giving day, inter-house sports and spelling competition. Several factors could lead to poor students' engagement. This study seeks to determine if social intelligence and self-esteem are correlated to academic engagement especially as Damina and General (2023) found a relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement. On the other hand, Omeodu (2021) found that students with positive self-esteem tended to be high in academic engagement and excel academically when provided with conducive learning environments. However, most existing researches often focus on cognitive aspects of learning and instructional methodologies, neglecting the social and emotional domain of students. It has been established that nurturing students' social intelligence and self-esteem is crucial in fostering academic success, as it can enhance academic effort and persistence.

Gender has been reported to be a critical factor when analyzing emotional intelligence and self-esteem. Gender refers to the roles associated with being male or female. Gender is commonly used to explain how society assigns certain responsibilities to males and girls. Gender refers to the behaviours associated with masculinity and femininity, as well as how people see their roles as male or female (Kauffman in Igbo et al., 2015). As a result, gender is linked to how people view themselves, with the majority of persons of the same sex identifying with specific characteristics. These characteristics influence children as they grow. Undoubtedly, the environment of a child influences his development (Igbo et al., 2015). Berk (as cited in Igbo et al., 2015) asserted that girls and boys were treated

differently from birth. Girls are clothed in pink, and parents are kind with the girl child. Furthermore, previous studies have found no significant gender differences in students' cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor skills in chemistry, mathematics, and science (Ezebube et al., 2023). They reported that male students outperformed female students in cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor skills. Svetlana (2018) found that male and female students fared similarly in English, with males outperforming females in Mathematics, Science, and Social Science, and females outperforming males in Arts. Ezebube et al., (2023) also found that female students have lower self-esteem than males. Similarly, boys were shown to have a somewhat greater degree of self-esteem than girls (Okafor et al., 2018). However, these findings have not been empirically proven to be the case among public secondary school students in Anambra State. Therefore, this study explored self-esteem as correlate of students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The issue of poor academic engagement among secondary school students in Anambra State has become a subject of significant concern for teachers, administrators, and parents alike. Recent observations by researcher as a teacher in a public secondary school in Anambra State suggested that student academic engagement in academic activities is seemingly on the decline. This lack of engagement manifests in several ways within the classroom. One notable instance of poor academic engagement is the increasing number of students who show little interest or enthusiasm during lessons. These students may appear distracted, disinterested, or disengaged from the topics being taught. They often fail to participate in class discussions or ask questions, which hinders their learning process. Another sign of disengagement is the lack of commitment to homework and assignments. Some students seem not to be completing their tasks on time, and when they do, the quality of work is often subpar. This reflects a broader issue of low motivation and a lack of personal responsibility toward academic success.

Furthermore, absenteeism is a significant concern. Some students regularly skip school, contributing to gaps in their learning and poor academic performance. This not only affects their personal development but also impacts the overall academic atmosphere in the school. These instances, among others, illustrate how poor academic engagement is increasingly becoming a pressing issue for secondary schools in Anambra State, requiring urgent attention from all stakeholders. An array of factors such as innate ability, the environment of the child, and parental socio-economic status among others could account for students' academic engagement. However, other psychological factors such as social intelligence and self-esteem fundamentally influence students' academic engagement and consequent academic achievement. It is a common knowledge in our public secondary school that some students lack self-confidence to participate effectively in group, or class discussion. They also struggle to interact effectively with their peers, suggesting low self-esteem. Such observations raise the question of whether these issues pertaining to self-esteem have any correlation with academic engagement among secondary school students in Anambra State. This study seeks to examine the correlation between social intelligence, self-esteem and academic engagement of public secondary school students in the area of study.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to examine self-esteem as correlates of students' academic engagement among public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between self-esteem and students' academic engagement among public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Examine the relationship between self-esteem and academic engagement of male and female secondary school students in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between self-esteem and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between self-esteem and academic engagement of male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between self-esteem and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship among self-esteem and academic engagement of male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted a correlational research design. The area of this study was Anambra State. Anambra State is a state located in South Eastern Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 21,272 senior secondary school two (SSII) students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population comprised of 9550 male students and 11,722 female students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State according to Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC, 2024). The sample of the study was 400 (200 male and 200 female) senior secondary school two (SSII) students from the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A multistage sampling procedure was employed to determine the sample of the study. In the first stage, simple random sampling was used to select two education zones, Ogidi zone and Onitsha zone. In the second stage, stratified random sampling was used to draw five public secondary schools from each education zone (Ogidi and Onitsha), making a total of 10 schools. Using cluster sampling procedure in the third stage, the first stratum of SS2 students in the 10 selected public secondary schools were participants in the study. Each stratum of SS2 class has 40 students, and the 10 classes yielded a total of 400 students representing 20% of the entire SS2 students of public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instruments for data collection were two instruments: Rosenberg Self-esteem scale and Hart et al. (2011) Student Academic Engagement in the Schools Questionnaire (SESQ). contains 21 items measuring students' self-esteem. Student Engagement in the Schools Questionnaire (SESQ) contains 28 items. Both Scales were structured on a 4- point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Sternberg Self-esteem Scale, (2011) Student Academic Engagement in the Schools Questionnaires are used for the study. Since the instruments were standardized and extensively used, they were not subjected to re-validation and reliability test. The researcher briefed three research assistants on how to administer the instruments to the respondents and intimate them on the purpose of the study and how to exhibit good human relationship during data collection. There was a follow up visit in order to retrieve these questionnaires from the respondents who were not disposed to complete theirs immediately. Out of 400 copies of the instruments administered to the respondents, 334 copies were correctly completed and returned in good condition. The 334 copies of instrument returned represented 83.5% return rate. The 66 copies of the instrument not well completed or lost represented 16.5% questionnaire. The 334 copies of the instrument returned were considered adequate and used for the analysis of data. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlational to determine the relationship between the variables. Hypotheses 1-4 were tested using Pearson 'r' at 0.05 level of significance. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 26 was used for the data analysis in schools in Anambra State?

Research Question one: *What is the relationship between self-esteem and students' academic engagement in Public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1. Pearson's Correlation between Self-esteem and Students' Academic Engagement in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	r	Remarks
Self-esteem Academic engagement	334	0.69	High positive relationship

The result of the Pearson's correlation (r) presented in Table 2 shows that the correlation between self-esteem and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State was 0.69. This value indicates a high positive relationship. This implies that as students' self-esteem increases, their academic engagement also increases and at a high rate.

Research Question two: *What is the relationship between self-esteem and academic engagement of male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2. Pearson’s Correlation between Self-esteem and Students’ Academic Engagement among Male and Female Students in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	r	Remarks
Male: Self-esteem Academic Engagement	164	0.69	High positive relationship
Female: Self-esteem Academic Engagement	170	0.70	High positive relationship

The result of the Pearson’s correlation (r) presented in Table 2 reveals that there was a high positive relationship between self-esteem and academic engagement among both male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is demonstrated in the r values which are 0.69 and 0.70 for the males and females respectively.

DISCUSSION

Relationship between Self-Esteem and Students’ Academic Engagement

The findings of the study revealed a high positive relationship between self-esteem and students’ academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State, suggesting that students with high levels of self-esteem tend to be more actively engaged in academic activities, demonstrating greater participation in classroom discussions, higher motivation to complete assignments, and an overall commitment to their studies. The finding of the study may have resulted because students with high self-esteem generally possess a strong sense of self-worth, which enhances their confidence in their academic abilities. The finding is in line with Okafor (2021) who reported that self-esteem significantly influenced students’ motivation and engagement in school activities. Similarly, Bagum et al., (2022) stated that students with higher self-esteem exhibit more positive attitudes toward learning and greater persistence in academic tasks. Zhao et al., (2021) opined that self-esteem served as a psychological asset that encouraged students to actively participate in educational settings, ultimately leading to improved learning outcomes.

The findings of the study also revealed that there was a significant relationship between self-esteem and students’ academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This suggests that self-esteem is a key determinant of students’ active involvement in their educational pursuits. The significant relationship observed in this study is consistent with the findings of Acosta-Gonzaga (2023), who found that self-esteem positively influenced students’ sense of academic self-efficacy, thereby enhancing their engagement levels. Similarly, Yidana and Arthur (2024) established that students with higher self-esteem were more likely to seek academic challenges and demonstrate perseverance in difficult subjects.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concluded based on the findings of the study that social intelligence has significant relationship with students’ academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings of the study showed that self-esteem has a high positive relationship with students’ academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Similarly, the findings of the study showed that social intelligence have a high positive relationship with academic engagement of male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher proffered the following recommendations:

1. Administrators of public secondary schools should collaborate with curriculum planners to integrate subjects and academic activities that promote Self-esteem among students. This can include group-based learning, conflict resolution training, and activities that enhance communication and interpersonal skills.

2. Principals of public secondary schools should design interventions that cater to the social learning needs of all students, ensuring equal opportunities for participation in leadership, teamwork and collaborative projects.

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